

To Study the Cotton Yarn to Make for the Knitted Fabric on Handle Properties

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Abstract

The knitted fabric structures greatly influence the dimensional, physical and comfort properties of fabric. In this work 100 % cotton knit fabric 1×1 rib, 2×1 rib was produced with 20 Ne, 25 Ne and 30 Ne ring yarn with varying stitch length on flat bed knitting machine. It is widely used to express the thickness of knit fabric. It is found, that fabric GSM decreases with the increased stitch length. GSM of 2x1 rib fabric is highest and 1x1 rib is lowest for both 20 Ne, 25 Ne and 30 Ne yarn count. The 1x1 rib structure having low fabric feel factor value leads to more comfort and soft feel appearance as compared to 2x1 rib having high fabric feel factor value and harsh feel. Bursting strength of 2x1 rib fabric is higher as compared to 1x1 rib structure knit fabric for 20 Ne, 25 Ne and 30 Ne yarn. Bursting strength also decreases with yarn fineness, i.e., lower for 30 Ne, 25 Ne yarn than 20 Ne yarn for all structures. It is found that 2x1 rib is highest value (Dry & Wet rubbing fastness) as compared to 1x1 rib structure knit fabric. The lower stitch length having higher dry & wet rubbing fastness because more compact structure and more GSM fabric. It is also found that 2x1 rib has highest value of Pilling propensity as compared to 1x1 rib structure knit fabric. The lower stitch length leads to more pilling propensity because of more compact structure and more GSM of fabric.

Keywords: Bursting Strength, Fabric Feel, Knit Fabric, Pilling Propensity, Rubbing Fastness

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1. Introduction

The knitted fabrics in general are more stretchable than the woven fabrics. The open structure of knitted fabrics also helps in moisture vapour transmission making it suitable for the comfort garments. Rib has a vertical cord appearance because the face loop wales tend to move over and in front of the reverse loop wales. As the face loops show a reverse loop intermeshing on the other side, 1x1 and 2x1 rib has the appearance of the technical face of plain fabric on both sides until stretched to reveal the reverse loop wales in between [1, 2]. The knitted rib structures are widely used in body lengths for outerwear, their main use is in providing welts, cuffs, and collars for garments with plain-knitted bodies and sleeves [3, 4]. Knit wear industry is rising at a faster rate over the globe and technological advancements contribute a lot in the success of industry. Knit wear fabrics are popular on account of their excellent properties of comfort, softness; sweat absorption, durability and softness. Quality of the fabrics of prime concern in placement of new ties between buyers and manufacturers, Consumers, now days, are becoming more and more concerned and aware of fabric quality and accept higher quality standards than any time in recent years [5]. Knit fabrics provide outstanding comfort qualities and have long been preferred as fabrics in many kinds of clothing. Knit fabrics are produced on different machines with different knit stitches and conditions to create different patterns and fabric types. The commercial design of knitted garments is a process that shares many important characteristics with other types of aesthetic design and engineering [6, 7]. Rib is a costlier and heavier structured fabric to produce than plain fabric. The main utilization of knitted rib structures is in providing welts, cuffs, and collars for garments with plain-knitted bodies and sleeves moreover the knitted structures are also widely used in body lengths for outerwear. Knitted fabrics are gaining popularity day by day because of the comfort and easy-care properties. Many studies were carried out in the past to study various

aspects of knitted fabrics [8]. The knitting parameters and the type of structure not only affect the comfort but also the performance properties of the knitted fabrics. Knitting machine gauge and the knitting stitch length are the two fundamental knitting parameters that directly affect all structure related properties of the knitted fabric.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Material

The cotton yarns used in this study have been prepared at DCM India Limited. The cotton yarns having 20, 25 & 30 Ne. Weft knitted fabric sample have been prepared on flat bed knitting machine with two different knit types 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures as shown in (Tables 1 to 3).

Table 1 - Test result of cotton yarn

S. No.	Parameters	Cotton Yarn 1	Cotton Yarn 2	Cotton Yarn 3
1	Count	20 s/1 combed	25 s/1 combed	30 s/1 combed
2	Um%	8.8	8.98	9.7
3	CVm%	11.12	11.35	12.28
4	Thin (-50%)	0	0	0
5	Thick (+50%)	12	14	15
6	Neps (+200%)	16	24	45
7	TPI	28	39	60
8	H	8.35	7.56	6.77
9	Sh.	2.02	1.78	1.58
10	CSP	2954	2830	2750
11	RKM	19.9	19.51	18.5
12	CV%	8.25	8.3	8.5

Table 2 - Specification for knitted fabric

Sr. No.	Count (Ne)	Type of Structure			
		1 x 1 Rib		2 x 1 Rib	
		Stitch length (mm)		Stitch length (mm)	
1.	20	3.5	4.5	3.5	4.5
2.	25	3.5	4.5	3.5	4.5
3.	30	3.5	4.5	3.5	4.5

Table 3 - Specification for the Cotton knitted fabrics

Sr. No.	Count (Ne)	Type of Structure	GSM (g/m ²)	Stitch Length	Wales per Inch	Course per Inch	Stitch Density	Thickness (mm)
1	20	1x1 Rib	375	3.5	29	23	667	2.5
2	20	1x1 Rib	329	4.5	24	18	432	2.3
3	25	1x1 Rib	345	3.5	32	24	768	2.2
4	25	1x1 Rib	305	4.5	25	19	475	2.0
5	30	1x1 Rib	319	3.5	33	24	792	1.9
6	30	1x1 Rib	295	4.5	26	21	546	1.8
7	20	2x1 Rib	343	3.5	26	24	624	2.4
8	20	2x1 Rib	302	4.5	21	20	420	2.7
9	25	2x1 Rib	318	3.5	27	26	702	2.5
10	25	2x1 Rib	286	4.5	22	21	462	2.5
11	30	2x1 Rib	294	3.5	28	26	728	2.3
12	30	2x1 Rib	265	4.5	23	22	506	2.4

Table 4 - Sample Plan

a. Methods

Before testing, the conditioning was done for 48 hours of all samples in standard atmospheric condition where temperature was $27 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity $65 \pm 5\%$ as per standards.

2.2.1. Pilling propensity

Pilling propensity of fabrics is determined by the machine Orbitor as per standards EN ISO 12945-1. Four tubular specimens are mounted on polyurethane pilling tubes and tumbled in the cork-lined box for an agreed number of revolutions. Specimens are usually prepared from samples which have been cleansed (wash or dry cleaned). This will help to preserve the useful life of the cork liners. Stringent quality control of the liners and the tubes is essential in order to ensure the critical demands of the standards are satisfied. ICI 444 modifies the cork lined box used for pilling tests by including one point in the center of each of the six (6) sides of the box. Snag Pod, which is used for BS 8479, has four (4) rows of 20 angled pins spaced evenly inside the octagonal chamber.

2.2.2. Rubbing test

As per standard ISO 105-X12 and AATCC 165 testing has been done. Crock Master is used to test the colour fastness to rubbing of carpets, knitted, laminates and printing inks. A colored test specimen is clamped and rubbed, under controlled conditions, against an undyed crocking cloth. Colour transferred to the crocking cloth is assessed in comparison with a standard Grey Scale for Staining. The Crock Master is normally supplied with the standard rubbing finger fitted.

2.2.3. Fabrics feel testing

Presently there are few instruments available for evaluating fabric handle objectively, like Kawabata evaluation system for fabrics and Fabric feel tester. In the present study fabric feel tester was used to obtain the objective evaluation about the fabric feel. Sample size of 24 cm diameter is used in the test. The fabric feel factor for the tested fabrics were obtained using the Equation 1. When the feel factor value is low the fabric would be softer and at higher value it's vice versa i.e., fabric would be harsher [9].

Calculations

$$\text{Feel factor (f)} = 26.58 + 20.65 * P_E - 0.436 * W_E - 0.131 * a + 5.064 * P_R - 0.361 * D_R \dots (1)$$

Where, P_E - Peak Height of Extraction curve (Kg)

W_E - Area under the curve for extraction curve (Kgmm)

A -Unload fabric across orifice for extraction curve

P_R -Peak height for radial curve (kg)

D_R -Peak distance for radial curve (mm)

2.2.4 Busting strength

The unique laser technology was used to measure distension provides the most accurate possible results. TruBurst2 Model 810 is aimed at the conventional fabric and apparel markets where bursting pressure up to 1000 kPa are required. TruBurst2 Model 801 targets the more specialized area of the market that requires the highest levels of accuracy at bursting pressures not exceeding 100kPa. TruBurst2 conforms to the ISO 13938-2 and ASTM D3786 test standards.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on fabric feel factor

Figure 1 demonstrates the effect of yarn count, structure and stitch length on fabric feel factor. Basically, fabric feel factor is related to one of the Kawabata comfort properties. When the feel factor value is low the fabric would be softer feel and at higher value it's vice versa i.e., fabric would give harsher feel properties. It has been observed from the figure 1 that with the finer yarn count, feel factor of the fabric increases irrespective of the knit structure due to reason of increase in twist/inch of yarn. It can be also observed from figure 1 that feel factor is higher for 3.5 mm stitch length as compare to 4.5 mm stitch length for both fabrics i.e., 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures. Further 2x1 rib fabrics exhibited higher feel factor as compared to 1x1 rib fabrics with same level of stitch length. The decrease in feel factor with increase in stitch length is due to increase in space required for each stitch for the same yarn count in both 1x1 and 2x1 rib structure. The values of fabric feel factor decreases may be due to increment in frictional properties. Rib fabrics with higher stitch length have lower feel factor in the fabric with same yarn counts.

Figure 1 - Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on fabric feel factor

Table 5 - Effect of 1x1 rib structure, yarn count and stitch length on fabric properties

S. No.	Count (Ne)	GSM (g/m ²)	Stitch length (mm)	Pilling grading	Bursting Strength (Kpa)	Rubbing cycles		Fabric Feel Factor
						Dry (20)	Wet (10)	
1	20	375	3.5	4.5	490	4	4	43.72
2	20	329	4.5	3.5	465	3	3	37.65
3	25	345	3.5	4.5	460	4	4	27.82
4	25	305	4.5	3.5	410	3	3	26.79
5	30	319	3.5	4.5	435	4	4	24.87
6	30	295	4.5	3.5	356	3	3	22.61

Table 6 - Effect of 2x1 rib structure, yarn count and stitch length on fabric properties

S. No.	Count (Ne)	GSM (g/m ²)	Stitch length (mm)	Pilling grading	Bursting Strength (Kpa)	Rubbing cycles		Fabric Feel Factor
						Dry (20)	Wet (10)	
1	20	343	3.5	5	547	5	4	48.12
2	20	302	4.5	4	471	4	3	45.97
3	25	318	3.5	5	480	5	4	44.19
4	25	286	4.5	4	425	4	3	37.14
5	30	294	3.5	5	460	5	4	34.74
6	30	265	4.5	4	410	4	3	33.21

3.2. Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on bursting strength

Figure 2 shows the effect of yarn count, knit structure and stitch length on fabric bursting strength. Bursting strength is an alternative method of measuring strength in which the material is stressed in all directions at the same time and is therefore more suitable for such materials. It has been observed from the figure 2 that with the finer yarn count, the bursting strength of the fabric decreases irrespective of the knit structure due to increase in porosity of the fabric. It has been also observed from (Table 5) and figure 2 that bursting strength decreases as the loop length increases from 3.5 to 4.5 mm for each yarn count in 1x1 rib knit structure. This is due to the fact that, when stitch length is less, no. of loops per square inch is more. Therefore, the resistance towards the force is more in case of less stitch length of fabric. Similarly, in (Table 6) bursting strength is decreasing with increase in stitch length as seen from the figure 2. The decrease in bursting strength with increase in stitch length is due to decrease in stitch density for the same yarn count in both 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures. Rib fabrics with higher stitch length have lower bursting strength in the fabric with same yarn counts. The results are in accordance with the findings of Mst. Sarmin Khatun [10-12], who stated that 2x1 rib fabrics exhibited higher bursting strength as compared to 1x1 rib fabrics.

Figure 2 - Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on bursting strength

3.3 Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on rubbing fastness

The extent of fastness to dry and wet rubbing is assessed visually comparison with arbitrary standards 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, where 5 denotes good fabric color fastness i.e., no change in color and 1 denotes poor fabric color fastness i.e., severe change. Figures 3 and 4 demonstrate the effect of yarn count and stitch length on dry and wet rubbing fastness respectively. It has been observed from the figures 3 and 4 that yarn count does not have any effect on dry and wet rubbing fastness the rubbing fastness of the fabric is same irrespective of the yarn count. It can be also observed from Table 5, figures 3 and 4 that dry and wet rubbing fastness is higher for 3.5 mm stitch length as compare to 4.5 mm stitch length for both fabrics i.e., 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures due to increase in fabric thickness. Further 2x1 rib fabrics exhibited higher dry and wet rubbing fastness as compared to 1x1 rib fabrics with same level of stitch length. Similarly, table 6 shows rubbing fastness decreases with increase in loop length as seen from the figures 3 and 4. The decrease in rubbing fastness with increase in stitch length is due to increase in space required for each stitch for the same yarn count in both 1x1 and 2x1 rib structure. Rib fabrics with higher stitch length have lower value of dry and wet rubbing fastness in the fabric with same yarn counts.

Figure 3 - Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on dry rubbing fastness

Figure 4 - Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on wet rubbing fastness

3.3. Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on Pilling Propensity

Figure 5 shows the effect of yarn count, knit structure and stitch length on pilling propensity of fabric. Pilling is a process that occurs on the surface of fabrics and leads to the formation of irregular clumps of fibers ranging from small to large, named “pills”, more or less anchored to the surface of the fabric. The extent of pilling is assessed visually comparison with arbitrary standards 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, where 5 denotes no change in fabric surface i.e., zero pilling and 1 denotes the maximum pilling. It has been observed from the figure 5 that the yarn count does not have any major influence on the pilling propensity of the fabric irrespective of the knit structure [12- 14].

It can be also observed from Figure 5 that pilling propensity is higher for 3.5 mm stitch length as compare to 4.5 mm stitch length for both fabrics i.e., 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures due to a smaller number of loops per inch. Further 2x1 rib fabrics exhibited higher pilling propensity as compared to 1x1 rib fabrics with same level of stitch length. This is due to more compact structure. It has been also observed from table 5 and figure 5 that pilling propensity decreases as the loop length increases from 3.5 to 4.5 mm in 1x1 rib knit structure. This is due to the fact that when stitch length is less the stitch density is more. Similarly, Table 6 shows that pilling propensity decreases with increase in stitch length as seen from the figure 5. The decrease in pilling propensity with increase in stitch length is due to decrease in stitch density for the same yarn count in both 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures. Results were supported by the findings of Daiva Mikucioniene [15], who said that rib knitted fabric gives substantially fewer pills than the interlock, rib 1×1, and plain knitted fabric because of less operated surface area.

Figure 5 - Effect of yarn count, stitch length and knit structure on pilling garding

4. Conclusions

In present study an attempt is made to study the influence of various parameters on the comfort properties knit fabric, fabric feel factor, bursting strength, pilling strength and rubbing fastness on different yarn count like 20 Ne, 25 Ne and 30 Ne for 2x1 and 1x1 structure rib 100% cotton knit fabrics. Therefore, from the various combinations of knit fabrics, GSM, Stitch length and yarn count range 20 Ne, 25 Ne and 30 Ne, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Stitch density is highest for 2x1 rib for all yarn count and lowest for 1x1 rib. The again stitch density is higher for fabrics made from finer count yarn compared to coarser count for all structures in fabrics. Also, GSM depends on yarn count, knit structure & dimensional properties of knit fabrics. It is widely used to express the thickness of knit fabric. Fabric GSM decreases with the increased stitch length.
- Stitch length has greater effect on both 1x1 rib and 2x1 fabric but more on 1x1 rib in the sense that the lesser the stitch length, the more compact the knit structures is, the higher the stitch density and fabric weight but the higher the stitch length, the more loose the fabric becomes and the lesser the stitch density and fabric weight.
- Fabric feel factor changes with stitch length i.e. for shorter stitch length value is higher than longer stitch length fabrics. The 1x1 rib structure has low fabric feel factor value for this low value is more comfort and soft feel compared to 2x1 rib is high fabric feel factor value shown fabric harsher feel knit cloth.
- Bursting strength of 2x1 rib fabric is higher compared to 1x1 rib structure knit fabric and for all yarn count ranges. Like loop length, bursting strength also decreases with yarn fineness, irrespective of the stitch length for both structures.
- Pilling propensity is higher for 3.5 mm stitch length as compare to 4.5 mm stitch length for both fabrics i.e., 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures due to less number of loops per inch and The decrease in pilling propensity with increase in stitch length is due to decrease in stitch density for the same yarn count in both 1x1 and 2x1 rib structures.
- It has been found according to as research work that 2x1 rib is highest value (Dry & Wet rubbing fastness) compared to 1x1 rib structure knit fabric. Lower value of stitch length gives more dry & wet rubbing fastness because more compact structure and more GSM fabric.

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